

Development of selective electrochemical detector for hydrazine in water samples using nickel hexacyanoferrate modified disposable gold electrode

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Abstract : Hydrazine and its derivatives are toxic and can cause several health hazards including cancer. It is highly challenging to develop a selective sensing technique for hydrazine in real samples. In this work, a new electrochemical sensor for hydrazine based on a nickel hexacyanoferrate chemically modified disposable gold barrel plated electrode (AuBPE/NiHCF) has been developed. AuBPE/NiHCF showed stable and well defined surface confined redox peak at 356 mV vs Ag/AgCl in pH 7 Na₂SO₄-NaOAc. Under an optimal cyclic voltammetric condition, the modified electrode showed a linear current response for hydrazine concentration in a range 0.5–10 mM with current sensitivity value of 35.32 $\mu\text{A}/\text{mM}$. Amperometric *i-t* method of hydrazine detection yielded current sensitivity and detection limit values 0.2052 $\mu\text{A}/\mu\text{M}$ and 51 nM respectively. The AuBPE/NiHCF is tolerable to co-existing interferences such as oxalic acid, citric acid, nitrite, dopamine and uric acid. Three different water samples were successfully analyzed for the hydrazine detection with appreciable recovery values.

Keywords : Hydrazine, water analysis, NiHCF, disposable gold barrel plated electrode.

Introduction

Hydrazine is a strong reducing agent. It is widely used in industry and agriculture as fuel, insecticides, explosives, rocket propellants and photographic chemical. It can easily adsorb on skin and penetrate to the body fluids and can cause cancer and hepatotoxicity. In further, it affects blood production and damage kidney too¹. Previously, many analytical methods based on colorimetric, spectrophotometric, potentiometric, chemiluminescence and titrimetric techniques were reported to detect trace levels of hydrazine in the environmental samples². Since the hydrazine doesn't have any chromophore, the above said conventional methods require series of derivatization procedures prior to the analytical measurements^{3,4}. Meanwhile, electrochemical techniques were reported as derivatization-less methodology for hydrazine analysis⁵⁻⁹. Here in we report a nickel hexacyanoferrate (NiHCF) modified disposable ultrathin gold barrel plated electrode (designated as (AuBPE/NiHCF)) system for selective electrochemical sensing of hydrazine in environmental water samples.

NiHCF, a polynuclear inorganic mixed valence transition metal complex, received considerable attention in

the electroanalytical chemistry. Previously in aim to prepare a stable NiHCF system various matrix such as carbon nanotube (CNT)⁷, graphitized meso porous carbon (GMC)⁸ modified glassy carbon electrode (GCE), graphite electrode⁵, thiol self assembled monolayers modified gold electrode⁹, sol-gel derived modified platinum electrode⁶ were used. Unfortunately, most of the reported procedures were having tedious fabrication procedures, and associated with surface regeneration problem in neutral pH^{7,8}. In this work, we used AuBPE as a versatile underlying electrode for efficient and stable modification of NiHCF film and for effective hydrazine electrochemical sensing. Note that the BPE is low cost, disposable and non surface polishable type working electrode. The BPE manufacturing technique holds many advantages, such as consistency of electro-active area and efficient electron transfer characteristic (due to the noble metal underlying surfaces). The BPE based disposable-type electrodes were already been used for some electro-analytical applications¹⁰⁻¹². First time in this work, we report AuBPE/NiHCF for sensitive and selective detection of hydrazine in pH 7 Na₂SO₄-NaOAc. Three different water real samples were successfully analyzed with appreciable recovery values.

Experimental

Chemicals and instrumentation : Nickel sulphate (Central Drug House), potassium ferricyanide (Merck), hydrazine sulphate extrapure (Sisco Research Laboratories) and other chemicals were of analytical grade, and used as received without further purification. Aqueous solutions were prepared using deionized and alkaline KMnO_4 distilled water. Voltammetric measurements were carried out using CHI model 660C electro-chemical work station, USA. The three electrode system consisted of AuBPE and its chemically modified form (CME) as a working electrode, Ag/AgCl with 3 M KCl as a reference electrode and platinum wire as a counter electrode.

Procedures : Scheme 1 provides a preparation procedure for the AuBPE/NiHCF modified electrode. In order to maintain the consistent working electrode surface, the cylindrical part of AuBPE was covered with non-conducting silicon tube. Electrochemically accessible surface area of the BPE electrode was measured using 2 mM $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ /pH 7 system as 0.0698 cm^2 . The AuBPE/NiHCF was prepared by potential cycling of AuBPE with 2 mM each of NiSO_4 and $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ dissolved pH 7 Na_2SO_4 -NaOAc solution (optimal) in a window 0–0.9 V vs Ag/AgCl at a scan rate (ν) 50 mV s^{-1} for twenty continuous cycles ($n = 20$, $n = \text{no. of cycles}$). After the experiment, the modified electrode was washed with copious amount of water and electrochemically pretreated again in the same potential window and medium (pH 7 Na_2SO_4 -NaOAc solution; $n = 20$). Three different kind of real samples; tap (drinking purpose), bore and well waters collected in and around VIT University, were subjected to real sample analyses.

Results and discussion

Electrochemical behavior of AuBPE/NiHCF :

Scheme 1 shows cartoon for the preparation of AuBPE/

NiHCF. Fig. 1A curve a is a continuous CV response of a AuBPE in 2 mM each of NiSO_4 and $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ dissolved pH 7 Na_2SO_4 -NaOAc medium. A well-defined reversible redox peak response (A1/C1) centered at apparent electrode potential ($E^{0'}$) = 356 mV and peak-to-peak separation (ΔE_p) = 36 mV respectively along with a feeble post redox peak (A2/C2) at $E^{0'} = 428 \text{ mV}$ vs Ag/AgCl and $\Delta E_p = 38 \text{ mV}$ were noticed.

The redox peaks were highly stable in nature (Fig. 1A, curve b). Calculated relative standard deviation (RSD) for the twenty continuous CV responses of the electrode in pH 7 NaOAc- Na_2SO_4 is 0.27%. This observation showed appreciable stability of the NiHCF chemically modified electrode in a neutral pH unlike to the conventionally prepared electrode with poor stability^{5,6,9}. The redox processes could be attributed to Na^+ intercalated with different NiHCF active sites¹³, as follows :

In the above equations, $\text{NaNi}_{1.5}^{\text{II}}[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{CN})_6]$ and $\text{Na}_2\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{CN})_6]$ are referred to be non-stoichiometric and stoichiometric forms of the NiHCF active sites, respectively. The observed $E^{0'}$ value in this work (356 and 428 mV vs Ag/AgCl) are appreciably matching with the redox potentials of the GCE/NiHCF@MWCNT and GCE/NiHCF@graphitized mesoporous carbon electrodes in pH 7 PBS^{7,8}. The electrochemical behavior of AuBPE/NiHCF is adsorption-controlled electron transfer in nature (double logarithmic plot of i_p versus scan rate (ν) is linear, $\delta \log i_p / \delta \log \nu = 0.94$ (Fig. 1B)) and pH independent characteristic (absence of any proton coupled electron transfer reaction, data not shown). These characteristics are similar to the electrochemical behaviors of previously reported NiHCF systems^{7,8}.

Scheme 1. Photograph of AuBPE (A), cartoon for the preparation of NiHCF on AuBPE underlying surface (B) and its mediated hydrazine oxidation reaction (C).

Electro-catalytic and amperometric sensing of hydrazine :

Comparative CV responses of the AuBPE/NiHCF without and with 2 mM hydrazine at a $\nu = 10$ mV/s in pH 7 NaOAc-Na₂SO₄ solution were given in Fig. 1(C) a and b. Control CV of AuBPE with 2 mM hydrazine is also displayed in the Fig. 1(C) c. As can be seen in the figure, the AuBPE/NiHCF showed a huge oxidation peak current at 0.4 V vs Ag/AgCl, where the A1/C1 and A2/C2 redox peaks appeared; which indicates mediated oxidation of hydrazine by the two redox couples. Note that when compared with AuBPE/NiHCF, the unmodified AuBPE showed about seven times lesser in the oxidation peak current value and 100 mV higher in oxidation potential. This observation implies efficient electrocatalytic response of the AuBPE/NiHCF to hydrazine.

Next, the effect of hydrazine concentration on the CV of the AuBPE/NiHCF was examined as in Fig. 1D. Upon increasing the hydrazine concentration, increase in the

anodic peak current was noticed. Plot of baseline corrected anodic peak current (i_{pa}) versus concentration of hydrazine was linear up to 10 mM. Calculated current sensitivity value by CV at $\nu = 10$ mV/s is 35.32 μ A/mM; which is about 31.2 times higher in sensitivity over the NiHCF graphite electrode⁵.

AuBPE/NiHCF was also subjected to the amperometric $i-t$ sensing of hydrazine at 0.4 V versus Ag/AgCl in pH 7 NaOAc-Na₂SO₄. A linear increase in the current signal against increasing hydrazine concentration was noticed (Fig. 1E). Respective calibration plot was linear in a range 10–100 μ M with a regression and sensitivity of 0.999 and 0.2052 μ A/ μ M respectively. The sensitivity value observed here is 28.7 and 1.7 times higher than our previous reports : GCE/NiHCF@GMC⁸ and GCE/NiHCF@f-MWCNT⁷, respectively. Calculated detection limit is 51 nM (S/N = 3). The modified electrode showed tolerance amperometric signal to environmental and biological interference chemicals such as oxalic acid (OA), citric acid (CA), nitrite (NO₂⁻), dopamine (DA) and uric acid (UA) (Fig. 1F).

Fig. 1. Typical cyclic voltammograms for (A) film formation (a) and stabilization (b) of NiHCF on AuBPE; (B) Effect of CV scan rate on AuBPE/NiHCF and (Inset B) plot of double logarithmic of peak current (i_p) vs scan rate (ν); (C) CV of AuBPE/NiHCF without (a) and with 2 mM of hydrazine (b) and AuBPE with 2 mM hydrazine (c); (D) CV responses of AuBPE/NiHCF with different concentration of hydrazine. Typical calibration plot (Inset Fig. 1D), amperometric $i-t$ responses of AuBPE/NiHCF (Fig. 1E) and its calibration plot (Inset Fig. 1E) and effect of interferents (Fig. 1F) on the AuBPE/NiHCF in pH 7 Na₂SO₄-NaOAc were given as Inset respectively.

Environmental water sample analyses :

In order to evaluate the practical applicability and feasibility of the sensor, three different water samples were tested by standard addition method. Analytical results were summarized in Table 1. As can be seen, there are no original detected hydrazine concentrations, which suggest absence any hydrazine contamination in the water samples. The recovery values of the known hydrazine spiked samples were $\sim 100\%$. This observation suggests appreciable suitability of present working electrode for various real-sample analyses.

Table 1. Results of the hydrazine real sample analysis obtained using a AuBPE/NiHCF

Sl. no.	Sample	Hydrazine concentration (μM)			Recovery (%)
		Original detected	Spiked	After spike	
1.	Tap water	0	50	51.12	97.8
			100	100.23	99.77
2.	Well water	0	50	51.28	97.5
			100	102.4	97.6
3.	Bore water	0	50	50.24	99.52
			100	101.28	98.73

Conclusion

NiHCF has been successfully prepared on a mass produced, disposable type ultra thin gold coated barrel plated electrode (AuBPE/NiHCF) by potential cycling method. Redox mechanism of the electrode follows surface confined electron-transfer pathway and pH independent electron transfer characteristics. The AuBPE/NiHCF showed 7 times higher in the electrocatalytic oxidation of hydrazine over the unmodified, AuBPE electrode. Cyclic voltammetric and amperometric *i-t* methods of detection of hydrazine showed calibration plots with linearity up to 10 mM and 100 μM respectively. The sensor showed

sensitivity value 205.2 $\mu\text{A}/\text{mM}$ and detection limit 51 nM. Detection of hydrazine in three different water samples was successfully demonstrated.

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